

(a) rabbit polyclonal anti-Ucp1 antibody (1:1000, cat. no. GTX10983, GeneTex)
goat polyclonal anti-rabbit IgG antibody with HRP(1:10000; cat. no. GTX26721, GeneTex)
(Theoretical MW =33 kDa)

UCP1 (20210430)

Validation statements on the manufacturer's website:

<https://www.genetex.com/Product/Detail/UCP1-antibody/GTX10983>

(b) rabbit polyclonal anti-Prdm16 (1:1000, cat. no. ab106410, Abcam)
goat polyclonal anti-rabbit IgG antibody with HRP(1:10000; cat. no. GTX26721, GeneTex)
(Theoretical MW =140kDa)

PRDM16 (20210430)

Validation statements on the manufacturer's website:

<https://www.citeab.com/antibodies/748339-ab106410-anti-prdm16-antibody>

(c) rabbit polyclonal anti-Pgc1 α antibody (1:1000, cat. no. NBP1-04676PCP, Novus)
goat polyclonal anti-rabbit IgG antibody with HRP(1:10000; cat. no. GTX26721, GeneTex)
PGC1 α (Theoretical MW =91 kDa)

PGC1 α (20210428)

Validation statements on the manufacturer's website:

https://www.novusbio.com/products/pgc1-alpha-antibody_nbp1-04676pcp

(d) rabbit polyclonal anti-Dio2 antibody (1:1000, cat. no. GTX81072, GeneTex)
goat polyclonal anti-rabbit IgG antibody with HRP(1:10000; cat. no. GTX26721, GeneTex)
DIO2 (Theoretical MW =31 kDa)

DIO2 (20210428)

Validation statements on the manufacturer's website:

<https://www.genetex.com/Product/Detail/DIO2-antibody-Internal/GTX81072>

(e) rabbit polyclonal anti-Cidea (1:1000, cat. no. ab8402, Abcam)

goat polyclonal anti-rabbit IgG antibody with HRP(1:10000; cat. no. GTX26721, GeneTex)

CIDEA (Theoretical MW =25 kDa)

CIDEA (20210421)

Validation statements on the manufacturer's website:

<https://www.abcam.com/products/primary-antibodies/cide-a-antibody-ab8402.html>

(f) rabbit monoclonal anti-Hsp70 antibody (1:4000, cat. no. ab45133, Abcam)

goat polyclonal anti-rabbit IgG antibody with HRP(1:10000; cat. no. GTX26721, GeneTex)

HSP70 (Theoretical MW =70 kDa)

HSP70 (20210422)

Validation statements on the manufacturer's website:

<https://www.abcam.com/products/primary-antibodies/hsp70-antibody-ep1007y-ab45133.html>

(g) rabbit polyclonal anti-Gapdh antibody (1: 5000, GTX100118, GeneTex)

goat polyclonal anti-rabbit IgG antibody with HRP(1:10000; cat. no. GTX26721, GeneTex)

GAPDH (Theoretical MW =36 kDa)

GAPDH (20190703)

Validation statements on the manufacturer's website:

<https://www.genetex.com/Product/Detail/GAPDH-antibody/GTX100118>